

REVEALING THE ACT OF BUILDING

Architecture as a process

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self-office

Architecture is a process. A very long one in fact. This process is never straightforward and it continuously moves back and forth, involving a rich yet complex net of stakeholders: from clients, investors, lawyers, to public workers, engineers, architects, and end-users.

But not only — it also involves changes in the program, awkwardly placed structures, materials on-site, and construction codes that do not accommodate the existing conditions. As architects, we aim to anticipate construction, but eventually it is somehow uncertain. It is precisely through this condition of uncertainty where architecture has the opportunity to explore new formal languages and question pre-established notions of good design.

In 2022, we were commissioned to refurbish an old watermill in Catalonia's rural northwest. Upon accepting the project, we found a house with its interior fully demolished and partially reconstructed. Due to the global financial crisis, the property remained in disrepair for years. This visual essay presents a series of thoughts and documents from this renovation project. They combine the pragmatism of economic and material means with our obsession for revealing the construction history of the house. This includes chronicling its alterations, unsuccessful endeavors, readaptations, new additions and juxtapositions — a series of actions which reflect the complexity of architecture as a dynamic process as it fluctuates over time and undergoes constant reassessment.

CHAPTER 2 DETAILS OF DEMOLITIONS

Is it relevant to differentiate between the original and the new if the house has been drastically modified? The understanding of the house 'as found' might become a new language worth to explore, a strategy which continues a process already started.

REVEALING THE ACT OF BUILDING

SECCIO CARBONS

CARBA	LONG	SECC	RECC	PARA CALIFICAT
1	400	45		10 2 plenas de 6mm
2	255	150		
3	280	240		
4	260	350		
5	350	270		decalaje de 10 x 15 x 15mm
6	215	270		Adosar 3 unes
7	315	300		
8	360	260		Ados. fura. de 10 x 15 x 15mm
9	330	310		decalaje plus de 10 x 15 x 15mm
10	310	340		Adosar
11	320	350		
12	500	400		
13	360	165		
14	400	160		
15	275	270		
16	400	400		10 2 plenas control de deformacio
17	320	280		
18	300	250		
19	310	400		Eme per altes
20	300	300		
21				
22				
23				
24				
25				
26				
27				
28	320	320		
29	320	320		
30	420	420		
31	330	330		
32	415	380		
33	420	440		
34	320	320		

List of salvaged beams, organised by section, length and construction anomalies (e.g. steel joints, screws, deformations) and disposition of the structural elements in quadrants in the ceiling plan.

A new vernacular language emerges by revealing the construction systems of the house which that are interconnected to each other. Like surgical procedures that dissect the existing structures and carefully complement and extend them.

REVEALING THE ACT OF BUILDING

- new additions
- salvaged elements
- refurbishment 2007
- demolitions
- original

This results in a sense of coherence and differentiation, making it nearly impossible to distinguish between the several interventions and the original construction. Thus, details don't need to be perfect or extraordinary. Many materials have edges that are not meant to be visible, yet these often are the most emotional edges to look at.

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